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Environment

Antibiotic contamination of fresh organic fertilizers and processed bio-based fertilizer products

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Abstract

Fertilizer prices have risen considerably in recent years, making the use of nutrient-rich organic side streams as a fertilizer more attractive. However, the use of such materials bears certain risks such as the introduction of unwanted pollutants, germs, or unbalanced nutrients into the environment. Antibiotics are a group of drugs used in large quantities in humans and animals and are therefore often found in organic waste streams that are used as fertilizers. Only a small proportion of the administered dose is absorbed and metabolized, while the significant part is excreted metabolized or unchanged and can remain in an active form. This study identified 14 antibiotics from the classes of tetracyclines (TCs), fluoroquinolones (FQs) and sulphonamides (SAs) in bio-based fertilizers (BBF) and discussed the effects of processing on residual concentrations. High levels of antibiotics were detected in manure, sewage sludge, and digestate. Composting in an extensive composting plant as one processing possibility had the potential to reduce TCs by 26% and FQs by 37% when sewage sludge with green waste was treated. Less antibiotic residues were detected in struvite and animal-based by-products. In addition, the nutrient concentration in processed BBF is often high, which means that lower amounts of fertilizer are used in agricultural systems. The low levels also mean that few antibiotics are spread.

1 | INTRODUCTION

Rising energy prices and resource scarcity, among other factors, have recently led to a significant increase in mineral fertilizer prices (Eisa et al., 2022). The production of ammo-

nium fertilizers from atmospheric nitrogen is associated with high energy and gas consumption, while phosphorus is largely extracted from rock, which is mainly available in a small number of countries such as Morocco, China, the United States, and Russia. However, the need for a sustainable economy is becoming apparent in a variety of sectors, and the idea of a circular economy means that recycled nutrients from waste materials are becoming more popular (Ritzén & Sandström, 2017). The availability of fertilizers as a prerequisite for ensuring the supply of food to the European population is also an important aspect (European Commission, 2015). Many projects have been launched to produce fertilizers from different types of waste materials and replace mineral fertilizers

Abbreviation: BBF, biobased fertilizer; DW, dry weight; FQ, fluoroquinolone; FW, fresh weight; HPLC, high-performance liquid chromatography; ICP-OES, inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy; LC, liquid chromatography; LOD, limit of detection; LOQ, limit of quantitation; MS, mass spectrometry; Na₂-EDTA, disodium ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid; RT, room temperature; S:N, signal-to-noise ratio; SA, sulphonamide; SPE, solid-phase extraction; TC, tetracycline; WWTP, wastewater treatment plant.

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(Sniatala et al., 2023). Regionally, a variety of waste materials are available that can be used to produce fertilizers, but there is often a lack of information about their potential for use as a fertilizer. In addition to the actual nutrient content, the ability to store the fertilizer, the technology to apply it, and the availability of the main nutrients for plants are relevant.

In addition to traditional agricultural fertilizers such as manure, slurry, and digestate (Roig et al., 2012), many other bio-based waste materials can be used as fertilizers or to produce fertilizers throughout Europe, such as animal by-products, sunflower seed hulls, and olive pomace. Sewage sludge in particular has an important role to play owing to its ubiquity and availability in large quantities. However, from 2029, the direct land application of sewage sludge from wastewater treatment plants (WWTPs) with a treatment capacity of $\geq 100,000$ population equivalent (PE) will be forbidden in Germany, while the recovery of phosphorus (P) will be mandatory (Bundesministerium der Justiz, 2017). Hence, alternatives and different types of sewage sludge-based fertilizers are being investigated and developed.

In a circular waste management system, the recirculation of pollutants presents a problem (van Asselt et al., 2022). Studies show that substances such as pharmaceutical residues remain in various animal-based fertilizers and in the products of WWTPs (Buta et al., 2021). Possible methods to recover nutrients with low levels of contaminants include precipitation processes, such as struvite precipitation, ammonium stripping, extraction from sludge ash, and biochar filtration systems where contaminants are adsorbed (Lima et al., 2022; Marcińczyk et al., 2022). A broad range of different organic and inorganic contaminants, depending on the origin of the raw material, may be present in organic waste. Due to their complex matrix, their analysis is often challenging; hence, indicator substances are analyzed to observe the potential contamination level of such products.

Antibiotics are a compound class used in animal husbandry and humans, making these compounds good indicators of the potential contamination level. Antibiotics are commonly found in wastewater and waste from the animal and meat industries due to their widespread use to treat bacterial infections in humans and animals and promote animal growth, which is still a common practice in some countries (Walia et al., 2019). Various studies reveal that an acute toxicity of antibiotics only occur at very high concentrations for most organisms. Instead, the risk is related to the resistance genes that are increasingly being developed and multiplied by bacteria when antibiotics are present and the competitive pressure is high (Rumky et al., 2022; Su et al., 2023; Zhao et al., 2023). The frequent use of antibiotics can lead to the spread of resistant or even multi-resistant germs and is therefore a topic of great concern worldwide (Tan et al., 2022). The deaths of an estimated 1.27 million people in 2019 were associated with resistant or multidrug-resistant common infections (World Health Organization, 2022). Although organizations

Core Ideas

- Most bio-based fertilizers of animal or human origin contain residues of antibiotics.
- Composting can contribute to the degradation of antibiotics.
- Ash and struvite from sewage sludge are hardly contaminated with antibiotics.

such as the World Health Organization, the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations or the European Union and governments worldwide recognize the need to track antibiotic use, the exact amount in circulation is uncertain as it is not recorded in many regions (Walia et al., 2019). Currently, 41 countries collect sales data for veterinary antibiotics, which provides a global estimate of around 93.3 tonnes sold in 2017 (Tiseo et al., 2020). Only a fraction of the prescribed dose of antibiotics is metabolized in the body, while a large proportion is excreted via urine or feces in an unchanged form (Qiu et al., 2016; Sarmah et al., 2006; Spielmeyer, 2018). Thus, large quantities of active antibiotics end up in the waste materials that serve as the basis for fertilizers and are potentially released into the environment. The fate and degradation pathways are complex and inadequately understood (Baquero et al., 2022).

This study aims to compare the contamination level of different raw materials of human and animal origin and of processed fertilizers with selected antibiotics and the potential of composting to remove antibiotics. By way of example, 14 commonly used antibiotics from the classes of sulphonamides (SAs), tetracyclines (TCs), and fluoroquinolones (FQs) were examined. The results will be given and discussed in relation to nutrient contents and possible land application loads for the different fertilizers, and the containing antibiotics will be compared.

2 | MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 | Sampling

2.1.1 | Sampling of local farm fertilizers

Fresh fertilizers were provided by local composting plants, biogas plants, farmers, fertilizer suppliers, and WWTPs in Saxony-Anhalt and Lower Saxony in Germany (Table 1). The samples were obtained either directly from the plants or were taken from larger quantities exceeding 1 metric ton. From this, a composite sample of 3–10 kg was taken by combining and mixing samples from three different spots of the heap; a smaller portion of the mixed sample was processed further for analysis. All samples were freeze-dried (Gamma 1–20,

TABLE 1 Detailed information on fresh local bio-based fertilizers (BBFs).

Raw material	Number of samples
Compost and plant-based materials	
Green waste compost (100%)	6
Biowaste compost (70% municipal organic waste and 30% green waste)	4
Sewage sludge compost (55% sewage sludge and 45% green waste)	11
Digestate and manure	
Digestate of mixed materials (~12% manure, 14% poultry dung with renewable plant materials)	5
Digestate of manure (mostly pig, containing small amounts of cattle manure)	4
Manure (cattle, pig)	2
Poultry dung	
Poultry dung from barn and litter husbandry	3
Sewages sludge	
Sewage sludge from local waste water treatment plants	9
Mineral materials	
Struvite collected from local WWTPs (no commercial product)	4

Abbreviation: WWTPs, wastewater treatment plants.

Christ, Osterode, Germany), ground (RS200, Retsch, Haan, Germany), and stored at 4–6°C until analysis.

2.1.2 | Sampling of processed fertilizers

Processed fertilizers were collected and exchanged within the Lex4bio project from which numerous properties are already published (Dong et al., 2023; Hernandez-Mora et al., 2024; Wester-Larsen et al., 2024). The project collected data on numerous nutrient-rich side streams and selected 16 out of over 160 prospective fertilizers across Europe for further studies (Table 2). The fertilizers were selected according to their different raw materials and processing strategies and were divided into phosphorus or nitrogen (N) fertilizers, according to their main nutrients, for further field trials. Another requirement for the data collection was that the products are already on the market or are produced at least at pilot scale and can be purchased in larger quantities for use in field trials. The materials were processed in various ways, mostly dried and pelletized to make them available for interregional distribution. For the determination of antibiotics, all the samples were treated in the same way and were freeze-dried (Gamma 1–20; Christ), ground (RS200; Retsch), and stored at 4–6°C until analysis.

2.2 | Analytical method for the extraction and determination of antibiotics

The extraction method of Lehmann and Bloem (2021), based on Jacobsen and Halling-Sørensen (2006), was extended slightly. While Lehmann and Bloem (2021) used five antibi-

otics from human medicine as an internal standard, in the present study they were also treated as target analytes and the internal standard was omitted. This enabled the method to be used to study matrices from human sources, such as sewage sludge or sewage sludge compost. In addition, the antibiotic doxycycline, which is frequently used in human medicine, was integrated into the method. These changes meant that a different liquid chromatography (LC) column had to be used from the one used by Lehmann and Bloem (2021) and the eluent gradient in the HPLC method had to be adjusted. With these modifications, 14 antibiotics from three structural classes are analyzed in this study (Table 3).

In this analysis, 0.75 g fine-ground, freeze-dried material was weighed in falcon tubes. The material was extracted with 20 mL 0.2 M citric acid buffer (pH 3.7) containing disodium ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (Na₂-EDTA) for 20 min in an ultrasonic bath, followed by a centrifugation step at 10,000× g for 10 min at room temperature (RT). The supernatant was transferred in a conical flask, and the pellet was extracted again with 20 mL 0.2 M citric acid buffer (pH 3.7) containing Na₂-EDTA, as described before. Supernatants were combined, and the pellet was extracted for a third time using 10 mL methanol (80%) containing 20% of citric acid buffer (pH 3.7). The extraction procedure was the same as that described above, but the supernatant was transferred into an extra falcon tube. The pellet was mixed with 10 mL methanol containing 1% formic acid and was incubated overnight at room temperature. The sample was centrifuged again the next day, and the methanolic supernatants were combined and concentrated to 5 mL using a vacuum concentrator (Eppendorf). This fraction was combined with the aqueous fraction in the conical flask, and different cleaning procedures were conducted. First, a liquid/liquid extraction with 10 mL of heptane was

TABLE 2 Raw materials and technology of production of the investigated processed bio-based fertilizers (BBFs).

	Acronym	Raw material	Technology
Compost and plant-based materials			
Compost	VAC	Green waste compost	Composting
Plant-based	BA1	Wheat and maize	Fermentation and distillation
	MAL	Malt germs	Pelletizing
Poultry dung			
	FEK	Chicken manure	Drying and pressing
	OPU	Chicken manure	Pelletizing
Animal-based by-products			
	MO14	Animal proteins, vegetable by-products	Pelletizing
	OG1	Meat and bone meal	Pelletizing
	BIO	Meat and bone meal, apatite, vinasse, chicken manure and potassium sulphate	Pelletizing
	MB1	Meat and bone meal	Pelletizing
	ECO	Blood and feather meal	Pelletizing
	OG2	Horn meal (pig bristles)	Hydrolysis
	MO13	Feather meal	Pelletizing
Mineral materials			
Ashes	EPH	Sunflower husk ash	Granulation
	ADC	Sewage sludge ash	Thermochemical process
	PLA	Poultry litter ash	Incineration
Struvite	CGO	Struvite from wastewater supernatant	Struvite precipitation

TABLE 3 Antibiotics that were representatively investigated in the different antibiotic classes in this study.

Antibiotic	Acronym
Fluoroquinolone	
Ciprofloxacin	CF
Difloxacin	DF
Enrofloxacin	EN
Norfloxacin	NF
Ofloxacin	OF
Sulfadiazine	
Sulfadiazine	SD
Sulfamethazine	SM
Sulfamethoxazole	SMZ
Tetracycline	
Chlortetracycline	CTC
Demeclocycline	DMC
Doxycycline	DC
Methacycline	MC
Oxytetracycline	OTC
Tetracycline	TC

conducted, and the aqueous fraction was collected, filled up to 100 mL with deionized water, and adjusted to pH 3 by adding

formic acid. The extract was vacuum-filtrated through a filter paper (Macherey-Nagel 85/90 BF) before a further cleaning step through SPE (solid-phase extraction) cartridges (Phenomenex Strata-X) was performed. The SPE cartridges were eluted with 3 mL methanol and 3 mL citric acid buffer (pH 3) for the conditioning of the cartridges before the samples were loaded on the SPE cartridge at a flow rate of 5 mL/min. Afterward, the cartridges were washed with 8 mL of water and dried under vacuum. For elution of the antibiotics, the cartridge was first eluted with 4 mL of methanol and, in a second step, with 4 mL of methanol containing 1% formic acid. The eluate was concentrated to 1 mL and then quantitatively transferred to a 2-mL graduated flask and filled up with methanol. The sample was then filtrated through a syringe filter holder (Wicom perfect flow, PVDF, 0.2 µm) into a vial. The measurement was conducted using a liquid chromatography mass spectrometry (LC-MS/MS) system (AB Sciex 4000 Q-Trap, and an EC-C18 column (Poroshell 120 EC-C18, 3.0 × 100 mm, 2.7µ; Agilent) was used for the separation of the antibiotics. Eluent (A) was water containing 77.08 mg/L ammonium acetate and 0.05% formic acid, and eluent (B) was methanol containing 0.05% formic acid. A gradient was used starting with 83% A, which decreased to 65% A within 13 min and further to 8% A in the next 3 min. Then, 8% A was held for 4 min, and the proportion of A raised to 83% again within 1 min and held at 83% for a further 8 min.

TABLE 4 Recovery rates (%) of different antibiotic compounds in a range of bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) of different matrices.

Analyte	Acronym	Compost ^a	Digestate and manure	Poultry dung	Animal-based by-products ^b	Sewage sludge	Struvite
Number of spiked samples		17	2	3	4	7	4
Ciprofloxacin	CF	3.8	15.6	30.7	56.6	23.6	43.7
Difloxacin	DF	3.4	18.0	29.7	62.0	34.6	45.2
Enrofloxacin	EN	2.4	11.5	28.9	57.2	32.7	40.8
Norfloxacin	NF	3.7	17.0	28.4	53.6	31.8	45.2
Ofloxacin	OF	4.0	19.2	28.0	48.7	36.8	43.7
Sulfadiazine	SD	20.0	37.4	26.0	35.8	30.0	40.7
Sulfamethazine	SM	14.7	34.1	30.9	43.9	27.2	39.3
Sulfamethoxazole	SMZ	23.5	34.5	36.1	54.0	28.9	38.0
Chlortetracycline	CTC	15.8	25.7	35.9	58.5	32.8	31.7
Demeclocycline	DMC	15.8	31.6	36.0	59.6	32.7	42.6
Doxycycline	DOX	10.9	24.4	38.5	75.7	29.8	34.5
Methacycline	MC	11.2	29.9	33.9	61.4	27.3	40.4
Oxytetracycline	OTC	28.7	37.1	31.5	51.6	36.4	43.0
Tetracycline	TC	23.6	39.1	32.1	53.6	39.9	38.7

^aBiowaste, green waste, and sewage sludge compost.

^bMeal from blood, meat, bone, feather, or horn and animal proteins.

2.3 | Method validation of the determination of antibiotics

The limit of detection (<LOD) was defined as the minimal signal with a signal-to-noise ratio (S:N) above 3. A quantification was carried out starting at a S:N of a minimum of 9. The S:N was calculated using the Analyst Software (Version 1.6.2). The S:N depends on the sample matrix, the analyte, and the purity of the sample, and therefore, the LOD and the limit of quantitation (LOQ) vary considerably in relation to the matrix of interest.

To determine the recovery rates, a representative amount of the samples was spiked with all analytes (666 µg/kg sample) and extracted in addition to a non-spiked sample. To allow possible interactions to take place, the sample was spiked, moistened and left to stand for at least 30 min. The amount of analytes in the unspiked and spiked samples was calculated and the recovery rates were estimated from the difference. In total, 37 samples were spiked and the recovery rates compiled according to the matrix, regardless of whether they were assigned to the processed or local samples (Table 4). All composts with a high proportion of green waste exceeding 30% in the composition are summarized for this purpose together, such as sewage sludge compost and green waste compost, as the matrix adsorbs the antibiotics particularly strongly. Digested samples from manure and plants are summarized along with all fertilizers made from animal-based by-products, such as meat and bone meal and feather meal. The extraction of different active ingredients from complex

matrices is difficult, and a compromise always needs to be made. Accordingly, recovery rates vary widely depending on the matrix and the analyte of interest, and the values given are only intended to improve the understanding of the results.

2.4 | Nitrogen and phosphorus

The freeze-dried and ground samples were determined using the CN analyzer (vario MAX cube C/N analyzer; ELEMEN-TAR), and total nitrogen was determined according to the Dumas combustion method. For the analysis of phosphorus, 1 g of the freeze-dried and ground samples were digested in aqua regia under reflux cooling, and the content of total phosphorus was determined by inductively coupled plasma atomic emission spectroscopy (ICP-OES; Thermo icap 6300)).

3 | RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 | Recovery rates in different matrices

The recovery rates varied greatly depending on the matrix and the analyte of interest, as shown in Table 4, so no extrapolation is made to the actual values. This severely limits the comparability of the measured values.

While composts, digestates, and sewage sludge often had low recovery rates especially for FQs of ~10%–20%, recovery rates can reach 45% in struvites and up to 60% in animal-based

by-products. Animal-based by-products seemed to adsorb less antibiotics than the other investigated materials. Struvite had the simplest matrix of all the samples tested and one of the best recovery rates. It consisted mainly of a magnesium–ammonium phosphorus salt, while the proportions of organic materials from sewage sludge residues were highly dependent on the degree of purification and the production method, but were often below 5%. Sewage sludge and digestates as well as compost had the most complex matrix and differed depending on the source material. A variety of compounds can react with the target analytes and undergo any type of reaction, but strong adsorption effects are described in particular for fluoroquinolones and tetracyclines (Harrower et al., 2021). In contrast to many other studies, the samples in the present study were moistened after spiking and allowed to react for at least 30 min. This may explain the comparatively low recovery rates and shows how strong the adsorption effects of the used materials are. The question of whether bound antibiotics retain their antibiotic effect or form inactive structures has so far only been investigated in a few studies and is still unclear (Aga et al., 2016).

Although there are many studies about optimizing methods to extract antibiotics from different matrices, only a few have dealt with antibiotics in composted materials (Ho et al., 2013; J.-W. Kim et al., 2022). J.-W. Kim et al. (2022) achieved recoveries of 60%–120% for TC and SA in manure compost with McIlvaine extraction buffer. Other studies optimized the extraction and achieved better results with citric acid buffer for FQ, SA, and TC in manure (Bajkacz et al., 2020; Lehmann & Bloem, 2021). However, due to the different matrices and the number of analytes to be determined in parallel, a more effective extraction of analytes presents a challenge. Further experiments with different solvents and different extraction methods from these complex matrices are required. It would also be important to identify and analyze reaction products that continue to show antibiotic effects.

3.2 | Antibiotic concentrations in fertilizers

Fertilizers based on feces almost always contain large quantities of antibiotics (Tables 5 and 6). The largest amounts of antibiotics were found in pig manure-based digestate, with a maximum of 8987 µg/kg dry weight (DW) doxycycline and a total sum of measured tetracyclines of 9043 µg/kg DW (Table 5). This was in line with expectations, as large quantities of antibiotics are often detected in manure, and except for penicillin, TCs are the most frequently used class of antibiotic substances in the region of origin of the samples analyzed, and indeed worldwide (Tiseo et al., 2020; Wallmann et al., 2019; Yang et al., 2022). It also confirms that the antibiotics are not significantly degraded during digestion and therefore pose a similarly high risk as unprocessed manure. In struvite, only

traces of the investigated antibiotic classes could be detected, if at all (Tables 5 and 6). When struvite is precipitated, most of the antibiotics remain in the sewage sludge, so that the ratio of contamination to nutrient is very low and in this respect struvite might be a good substitute for mineral fertilizers. Most of the digestates and sewage sludge composts examined contained at least traces of antibiotics (Table 5). Here, the question arises as to whether lower contents of antibiotics indicate a degradation or dilution effect by being mixed with plant materials in their processing. This question will be addressed more in detail later using the example of sewage sludge composts. In comparison, the antibiotic concentrations in animal-based by-products were low, as many antibiotics are largely excreted unmetabolized (Aga et al., 2016; Pindell et al., 1959), and as expected, no antibiotics were found in ashes where organic components were destroyed at high temperatures. Traces of antibiotics were also detected in green waste compost. This could be attributed to the composting plant sampled, which processes, among other things, sewage sludge and thus can lead to cross-contamination, or to the processing of green waste from public parks and biowaste composts, where pet feces may be present.

Table 6 shows the concentrations found in the BBFs from the Lex4Bio project. Figure 1 visualizes the results summarized in Tables 5 and 6, showing the number of samples per matrix, how many of these samples are contaminated with one of the three antibiotic classes tested, and the mean and maximum concentrations. The categories were compiled according to the original material and the corresponding processing steps. In summary, it can be concluded that mineral fertilizers can be produced almost free of antibiotics by burning organic material or precipitating the nutrients, while fertilizers made from animal by-products are low in antibiotic residues and have a higher content of organic residues. However, antibiotic residues are found in feces and are not easily removed by composting or fermentation.

3.3 | Estimated application rates and loads

Fertilizers contain varying amounts of nutrients; thus, different application rates need to be considered in the risk assessment regarding the input of antibiotics into the environment with BBFs. The estimated application quantity of antibiotics with different fertilizers was calculated for an exemplary maize field with a P₂O₅ requirement of 72 kg/ha and nitrogen requirement of 160 kg/ha N (Figure 2 and Table 7). The predicted amounts of antibiotics that are applied via the different fertilizers are shown in Figure 3. Due to the small amount of nutrients in composts, more of these materials need to be applied to fulfil the nutrient demand. Struvite, for example, which is rich in phosphate, can be used almost like a mineral fertilizer, resulting in a relatively small amount

TABLE 5 Sum of antibiotics per antibiotic class found in locally collected fresh bio-based fertilizers (BBFs), the number of samples per matrix with antibiotic contents above limit of quantification (LOQ), and their mean and maximum values.

Fertilizer	Total		FQ		SA			TC		
	<i>n</i>	<i>n</i>	Mean (µg/kg)	Max	<i>n</i>	Mean (µg/kg)	Max (µg/kg)	<i>n</i>	Mean (µg/kg)	Max (µg/kg)
Compost and plant-based materials										
Greenwaste compost	9	0	–	–	0	–	–	0	–	–
Biowaste compost	4	1	24.0	24.0	1	27.8	27.8	1	1.7	1.7
Sewage sludge Compost	11	9	59.8	201.9	1	17	17	9	90.3	273.6
Digestate and manure										
Digestate of manure	4	3	11.4	32.2	3	10.2	18.8	4	3155.1	9043
Digestate of mixed materials	5	2	46.9	74.5	2	146.9	242.3	3	427.6	615.1
Manure	2	2	5.7	11.3	2	2.5	2.8	2	488	906.2
Poultry dung										
Poultry dung	6	5	27.7	43.3	4	3.6	6.6	2	135.7	264.2
Sewage sludge										
Sewage sludge	9	9	876.7	1607.7	2	27.2	41.5	9	278.4	570.7
Mineral materials										
Struvite	4	2	90.7	137.5	1	3.1	3.1	0	–	–

Abbreviations: FQ, fluoroquinolone; SA: sulfonamide; TC, tetracycline; –, not detected.

TABLE 6 Sum of antibiotics per antibiotic class found in the processed bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) collected and studied in the Lex4Bio project.

Acronym	Fertilizer	FQ (µg/kg)	SA (µg/kg)	TC (µg/kg)
Compost and plant-based materials				
Compost	VAC	Green waste and compost	–	–
Plant-based	BA1	Wheat and maize	–	–
	MAL	Malt germs	–	–
Poultry dung				
	FEK	Chicken manure	43.3	<LOQ
	OPU	Chicken manure	22.5	–
Animal-based by-products				
	MO14	Animal proteins, vegetable by-products	–	–
	OG1	Meat and bone meal	–	25.5
	BIO	Meat and bone meal, apatite, vinasse, chicken manure and potassium sulphate	LOQ	<LOQ
	MB1	Meat and bone meal	–	<LOQ
	ECO	Blood and feather meal	22.5	<LOQ
	OG2	Horn meal (pig bristles)	–	–
	MO13	Feather meal	–	–
Mineral materials				
Ashes	EPH	Sunflower husk ash	–	–
	ADC	Sewage sludge ash	–	–
	PLA	Poultry litter ash	–	–
Struvite	CGO	Struvite from wastewater supernatant	<LOQ	<LOQ

Abbreviations: FQ, fluoroquinolone; LOQ, limit of detection; SA: sulfonamide; TC, tetracycline.

FIGURE 1 Illustration of antibiotics in the local samples and the fertilizer samples provided by Lex4Bio, compiled in categories according to their source material and processing (n = number of samples). FQ, fluoroquinolone; SA: sulfonamide; TC, tetracycline.

FIGURE 2 Illustration of total nitrogen and phosphorus content in the local samples and the fertilizer samples provided by Lex4Bio, compiled in categories according to their source material and processing. DW, dry weight.

of antibiotics applied compared with other fertilizers, while sewage sludge, compost, and manure make a significant contribution. Despite the highest antibiotic content in sewage sludge, a similar or even larger amount of antibiotics can be applied via manure application.

The issue concerns the threshold at which contaminants begin to disrupt the soil ecosystem and outweigh positive effects, such as the addition of organic matter. Few studies have investigated whether resistance genes persist and spread in the soil in the long term as a result of organic

TABLE 7 Calculation of the amount of bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) in fresh weight (FW) to fertilize an exemplary maize field (160 kg/ha N and 72 kg/ha P₂O₅) based on the N and P content of the investigated fertilizers.

Fertilizer	Application rate calculated by total N (t/ha in FW)	Application rate calculated by P ₂ O ₅ (t/ha in FW)	Factor that defines the application rate
Biowaste and green waste compost, plant based materials	3.1–28.3	11.7–16.6	Mostly N
Sewage sludge compost		2.5–8.9	P
Digestate of mixed materials	24.4	1.5–17.5	Mostly P
Digestate of manure		3.2–16.1	P
Manure		3.3–33.7	P
Poultry dung		0.9–5.1	P
Sewage sludge		2.7–29.8	P
Animal-based by products	1.2–1.5	0.5–1.0	N or P
Ashes		0.4–1.8	P
Struvite		0.3–0.4	P

FIGURE 3 Estimated loads of antibiotics to maize by bio-based fertilizers (BBFs) when fertilized at a rate to deliver 72 kg/ha phosphate or 160 kg/ha nitrogen. FQ, fluoroquinolone; SA, sulfonamide; TC, tetracycline.

fertilization. Research shows a significant increase in resistance genes following fertilization with manure or sewage sludge, but also a subsequent return to background levels over the course of the year (Muurinen et al., 2017; van den Meersche et al., 2020).

In an overview of pollutants such as heavy metals, antibiotic resistance genes, microplastics, or new chemical groups such as flame retardants, Bünemann et al. (2023) argue that soil is more resilient than is commonly thought and has the ability to adsorb and degrade various contaminants. Long-term studies, particularly on the use of sewage sludge, show no noticeable negative effects. They therefore consider it acceptable to tolerate moderate levels of pollution, such as those found in many European regions, and suggest that the con-

trol and prevention of pollution sources should be improved (Bünemann et al., 2023).

3.4 | Changes in antibiotic levels during composting

To date, only a few studies have examined the degradability of antibiotics during composting, but most studies indicate a significant reduction (Ezzariai et al., 2018), as also shown in Table 8. In some studies, however, hardly any reduction was observed or, in other cases, only after a long period of time (Chen et al., 2021; Dolliver et al., 2008; H. Liu et al., 2019). The causes of the reduction and elimination pathways have

TABLE 8 Literature overview of studies on the degradability of antibiotics during composting.

Antibiotic class	Degradation efficiency	Material	Composting	Reference
Chlortetracycline	Efficient	Spiked broiler and hog manure	Laboratory-scale composting for 42 days	(Bao et al., 2009)
Sulfonamides Fluoroquinolone	Poor efficiency Effective	Spiked sewage sludge with food waste	Laboratory-scale composting for 28 days	(Chen et al., 2021)
Sulfamethazine Chlortetracycline	No degradation Declined rapidly	Spiked turkey litter	No disturbance, managed compost, and	(Dolliver et al., 2008)
Sulfamethazine Chlortetracycline	Declined Declined	Spiked pig manure with sawdust	Laboratory and field-scale composting for 40 days	(K. R. Kim et al., 2012)
Sulfonamide Quinolones Tetracycline	Dissipation above 70% 3–74 days half-life 7–27 days half-life	Swine manure	Laboratory-scale composting under environmental conditions for 28 days	(H. Liu et al., 2019)
Sulfonamide	Completely removed	Manure-straw mixture	Aerobic composting for 35 days	(B. Liu et al., 2015)
Tetracycline Fluoroquinolone	75% degradation Persistence	Sewage sludge with palm wastes	Field-scale composting for 120 days	(Khadra et al., 2019)
Fluoroquinolone	Removal efficiencies over 85%	Spiked sewage sludge with sawdust	60 L composting and 0.5 L incubation with three aeration strategies	(Zhang et al., 2019)
Sulfadiazine Tetracycline	Effectively removed: over 90%, composting accounted for 31%	Swine manure with mushroom residues	Composting with a succession of treatments	(W. Liu et al., 2023)
Tetracycline	70%–90% degradation	Swine manure	Pilot-scale composting for 52 days	(Wu et al., 2011)
Tetracycline Fluoroquinolone Sulfonamide	All completely removed	Spiked broiler manure	Composting in 12-L containers for 40 days	(Ho et al., 2013)
Tetracycline Fluoroquinolone Sulfonamide	98% removed 98% removed 92% removed	Spiked human feces with sawdust	Laboratory-scale composting for 20 days	(Shi et al., 2016)

been rarely investigated (Spielmeyer, 2018). Among other studies, those of Shi et al. (2016) and Spielmeyer (2018) show that in addition to process temperature, adsorption to the co-compost material plays a crucial role.

In the present study, 11 sewage sludge composts and nine sewage sludges were investigated for contamination by antibiotic residues and compared. The composting plant from which the samples were obtained used an extensive process. At the beginning of composting, sewage sludge was mixed with green waste (60/40% v/v). Overall, the compost matured for 2–3 months in the open air and was turned two to three times. Temperatures of around 60°C were reached in the main decomposition phase. Sulfonamides were found in very low concentrations, or at concentrations below the detection limit, while tetracyclines and fluoroquinolones were found at concentrations of up to 8000 µg/kg DW. Although there is uncertainty due to insufficient recovery, an attempt is made to estimate the degradation during composting based on the measured contents. First, the dilution effect due to green waste was compensated for by offsetting the 55% fraction of green

waste in the sewage sludge compost. In order to compare both the extractable fractions of the antibiotics and the fractions adsorbed on the particles in this analysis, the recovery rate was also taken into account by calculating the expected concentrations.

Tetracyclines and fluoroquinolones were found in sewage sludge in varying concentrations, while on average composted material shows a reduction by 26% and 37%, respectively, compared to the fresh sewage sludge (Figure 4). Based on these assumptions, a moderate degradation could therefore be assumed, but in contrast to data in the literature (Table 8), no rapid or effective degradation of TC and FQ could be confirmed. This may be due to the composting plant being extensively operated. Complete degradation may require conditions with higher temperatures, good aeration, or other intensive process parameters. This indicates that not every type of composting is suitable for TC and FQ degradation. However, dilution effects and adsorption to co-compost material usually lead to a low detection of antibiotic concentrations in the mature compost.

FIGURE 4 Calculated antibiotic contents in fresh sewage sludge and at the end of the composting process (after 2–3 months), taking into account the different recovery rates and the proportions of green waste in the compost. FQ, fluoroquinolone; SA: sulfonamide; TC, tetracycline.

3.5 | Limitations

The study examines the contamination of various fertilizers with antibiotics. However, several limitations should be noted. The low recovery rates of antibiotics in some materials increase the uncertainty of concentration measurements and negatively affect the lower limit of detection. Additionally, the fertilizers analyzed represent a heterogeneous group that is highly dependent on several parameters, such as process variables or seasonal differences in medication, meaning that each batch may differ. Therefore, the findings can only be partially generalized to other comparable studies.

4 | CONCLUSIONS

In this study, bio-based fertilizers of various origins were analyzed for their content of 14 commonly used active substances from three classes of antibiotics. It was shown that large amounts of antibiotics are present in animal and human excreta and that some of the antibiotics remain after digestion in biogas plants and after composting. The reduction of the antibiotic load during composting was estimated using 11 sewage sludge composts and nine sewage sludges. Assuming that the recovery rate reflects the adsorption to matrix components, a reduction in antibiotic residues of up to 37% was estimated in composted sewage sludge compared with fresh sewage sludge. In contrast, precipitation products such as struvite, animal-based by-products such as meat and bone meal, and ash products contain low levels of antibiotic residues and thus can be used as low-pollutant mineral or organic fertilizers

with respect to antibiotics. In an example of typical fertilization of a maize field, it was shown that the highest loads of antibiotics, up to 3000 mg/ha, are applied with manure, both digested and unprocessed. Additionally, with sewage sludge and sewage sludge compost, the investigated samples could apply up to 1500 mg/ha of antibiotics. In contrast, the amounts introduced through struvites, ashes, and animal by-products are very low due to their low content and high nutrient levels.

Despite the risk of BBFs containing drug residues, the use of manure and other nutrient and carbon-rich materials is an important part of the circular economy and has many positive effects on soil life and the environment (Diacono & Montemurro, 2010). Therefore, further studies are recommended to evaluate more precisely the risks posed by antibiotics and their fate during digestion and composting.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS

Sophia Albert: Conceptualization; investigation; methodology; visualization; writing—original draft; writing—review and editing. **Elke Bloem:** Conceptualization; methodology; supervision; writing—review and editing.

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CONFLICTS OF INTEREST INTERESTS

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY STATEMENT

Data will be made available on request.

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